

Original Research

Gender Board Directors: Moderating the Effect of Green Accounting and Eco-Efficiency on Firm Value

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Abstract

The study aims to test whether gender has a moderating effect on green accounting and eco-efficiency on firm value. The population 90 companies were selected using purposive sampling technique, the research sample was 10 companies with a period of 5 years (2019-2023) so that the number of observations was 50. The results showed that green accounting had a negative and insignificant effect, eco-efficiency had a negative and insignificant effect on firm value, gender of the board of directors was able to moderate green accounting on firm value and was unable to moderate eco-efficiency on firm value. The implications of the research are expected to be taken into consideration by all property and real estate companies that the presence of women in the board of directors affects decision making in increasing company value, the results of this study include policy suggestions for policy makers so that in a company it is mandatory to have a woman in the board of directors because considering that there are no official regulations that require the involvement of women in the board of directors in property and real estate companies. The novelty of this research is to add the gender moderation variable of the board of directors.

Keywords: Eco-Efficiency, Gender Direksi, Firm Value, Green Accounting.

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Introduction

In Indonesia itself is one of the countries with environmental issues that are quite alarming, this is marked by the fact that Indonesia is a country that occupies the second position in terms of plastic waste in the oceans, food waste that reaches 40 tons per year or 115-183 kg per capita per year through this pile of garbage will trigger an increase in gas emissions every year, in this case the government launched a program in order to reduce gas emissions, the program is Circular Economy, there are 5 priority sectors in this program including construction, food & beverage, textiles, electronics and plastic waste.

This research will be conducted on property and real estate companies listed on the IDX and meet the predetermined sample criteria. The reason for using property and real estate companies is because property and real estate companies are one of the sectors engaged in land and building development and are one of the providers of facilities and infrastructure as a complement. This sector is also the most attractive investment instrument for investors, this is because the demographic conditions in Indonesia have a large enough population and the increase in population is considered fast every year along with the increase in population and residential land, which is the reason investors buy property also because the price tends to increase every year this is because the property and real estate sector is one of the investments that is long-term and follows economic growth. The property industry is also one of the contributors to global carbon emissions, from the construction process to daily use, property requires resources and energy that can produce significant emissions (www.hukumonline.com, 2023).

This study will use the gender moderation variable of the board of directors because it considers several facts from previous research results which say that women are considered more sensitive than men in social matters, and women tend to focus more on qualitative results so that the involvement of women in the board of directors is a stimulant for environmental reporting (Adams, et al 2012).

There are several studies that say that the diversity of directors cannot moderate the effect of green accounting on firm value because the number of female directors in the company is still only about 30% of the total number of directors, so it has not shown any effect on the company's value (Aisanafi, et al 2022).

Other research results also say that the gender diversity of the board of directors affects the decrease in the allocation of company resources to carry out environmental activities, this is because the presence of women in the Board of Directors is very low, less than 15% (Kartana, 2024).

Devika, F., et al (2020) said that female board of directors has a strengthening role in moderating the relationship or influence of corporate social responsibility disclosure on company value. With the presence of women in the company, the company is considered to have implemented good governance practices. The involvement of women in the ranks of the company's board of directors and board of commissioners reflects the absence of discrimination in the company, meaning that the company provides opportunities for

anyone to become part of the company's board, this perception will increase the company's reputation and value to investors.

Given the increasingly concerning environmental issues in Indonesia, as well as the gap in the results of previous research, this is an opportunity for further research. The novelty of this research lies in the moderating variable of gender board directors. There are several gaps in research results that say that the gender board directors cannot moderate corporate social activities such as green accounting on firm value due to the very small number of women on the board of directors. therefore, in this study Gender board directors are expected to strengthen the influence of green accounting and eco-efficiency on firm value.

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Hypotheses

The effect of green accounting on firm value

Green accounting is often defined as accounting in which companies identify, measure, assess and disclose the costs associated with the company's activities related to the environment. Legitimacy theory is a theory that can describe important accounting because important accounting is an accounting science that presents information related to accounts that reveal company financing as an effort to protect the surrounding environment.

In addition, signal theory can also describe green accounting, because if a company applies the concept of green accounting, it will give a positive signal to investors that the company cares about the surrounding environment, so that it will attract investors to invest their capital in the company.

This is supported by the research results Faranika (2023) & Saputra (2023) which state that this important green accounting has a significant influence on company value green accounting is not only concerned with financial aspects and relevant subjects, but also involves accounting fields that have social and environmental dimensions. If green accounting practices are integrated into the annual report, this has the potential to shape a positive image for the company, especially in an effort to create a favorable impression or perception related to corporate identity. while Sugiyarti, et al (2023) say that firm value cannot be influenced by green accounting because environmental disclosure is a strategy that can be felt in the long term which cannot be felt in the short term by investors. Based on the description and research that says that green accounting can increase firm value and is supported by existing theories, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₁: Green accounting has a positive effect on firm value.

The influence of Eco-efficiency on firm value

Eco-efficiency is a concept applied by companies with the aim of improving the environment in the company's operational activities so that later it can increase the share price and of course will increase the value of the company. This concept can improve the environment through reducing the environmental impact per unit generated from production (Kesaulya, 2022).

Legitimacy theory and signaling theory are also related to the concept of Eco-efficiency because Eco-efficiency is a concept applied by companies with the aim of improving the environment in the company's operational activities by trying to minimize pollution resulting from the company's products so that through this concept it will increase the company's stock price and of course will increase the company's value and this concept will also be a positive signal from the company to investors which will attract investors to invest their capital in the company.

Dewi et al (2020) said that Eco-efficiency has an impact on company value while Yuliandhari (2023) said that eco-efficiency has no effect on firm value. With the ISO 14001 certificate owned by the company, it means that the company carries out operational activities rationally with good environmental management, so that adverse impacts on the environment can be reduced and prevented by not paying attention to the impact of company activities, and the company's value will increase. increases when the company's profit applies the concept of economic efficiency because the company's profit is environmentally friendly and the investment response increases along with the number of shares sold and the increasing stock price.

H₂: Eco-efficiency has a positive effect on firm value.

Gender board director moderates green accounting on firm value

Gender socialization theory states that there are differences in nature and behavior between men and women, where men tend to be more relationship-oriented, while women tend to be more relationship-oriented, create interpersonal trust and are considered creative in solving problems.

Rismawati (2019) said that female directors understand the business market segment better than men and this can balance the quality in the company's profit-making process, provide extensive knowledge and understanding of the company's markets and consumers so that the impact of innovations taken will ultimately increase the value of the company. Diez, et al. (2022) stated that men and women approach decision-making and assess the legitimacy of their organizations in different ways and the presence of a large number of female leaders is expected to increase CSR practices.

In addition, Sanchez, T. et al. (2021) also said that female directors are more motivated to engage in philanthropic and charitable activities so that they can improve company performance and CSR implementation. Based on the description of the research results and the explanation above, it is hoped that the gender of directors can strengthen the effect of green accounting on firm value, so the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H₃: Gender board director strengthens the effect of green accounting on firm value significantly positive.

Gender board director moderates Eco-efficiency on firm value

Gender socialization theory states that there are differences in nature and motivation between male and female directors, so male directors are more likely to be leadership-oriented while female directors are more likely to be oriented towards building relationships, creating interpersonal trust and are considered creative in solving problems. The difference in leadership is considered to have an impact on company decision making.

Rismawati (2019) said that female directors understand the corporate governance market segment better than men and this can develop quality in the corporate governance decision-making process, provide extensive knowledge and understanding of the corporate governance market and consumers so that the impact of decisions taken will ultimately increase company value besides that Devika, F., et al (2020) said that female board of directors has a strengthening role in moderating the relationship or influence of corporate social responsibility disclosure on company value. The involvement of women in the ranks of the company's board of directors and board of commissioners reflects the absence of discrimination in the company, meaning that the company provides opportunities for anyone to become part of the company's board, this perception will increase the company's reputation and value to investors, so the hypothesis that can be formulated is as follows:

H₄: Gender board directors strengthen the influence of Eco-efficiency on firm value significantly positive.

Material and Method

This type of research is associative research with a quantitative approach. This research was conducted on the Indonesia Stock Exchange through its website, www.idx.co.id. The data collection method that will be used in this research is the survey method. The population in this study were all property and real estate companies that have

been listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) in 2019-2023, amounting to 90 populations while the sample selection in this study used purposive sampling techniques. The final total sample in this study was 50, meaning that only 10 companies met the sample criteria. The sample used in this study is very small, this is due to the use of very specific measurements, namely the presence of women board directors. The type of data used is quantitative data. Quantitative data used in the form of financial reports and sustainability reports of property and real estate companies

Green accounting is measured using the percentage of CSR costs paid by the company from its net profit, eco-efficiency is measured using ownership of ISO 14001 certification, firm value is measured using Tobin's Q while gender of directors is measured using the number of female directors divided by the total directors. Company data was analyzed using Eviews 12.

Research results

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variabel	Firm Value	Green accounting	Eco-efficiency	Gender board director	Profitability	Leverage	Likuidity
Mean	0.914216	0.020315	0.220000	0.242288	0.033684	0.909870	2.963651
Median	0.913555	0.004082	0.000000	0.250000	0.035138	0.506699	2.304856
Maximum	2.559604	0.190826	1.000000	0.500000	0.260039	3.788211	11.39856
Minimum	0.331977	-0.009410	0.000000	0.090909	-0.382095	0.122831	0.674138
Std. Dev	0.340591	0.037725	0.418452	0.089970	0.078890	0.806066	2.539510
Observations	2.219791	2.653417	1.351853	0.401448	-2.413235	2.193483	2.016907

Based on the results of the descriptive test above, the average, maximum, minimum and other values of each variable are obtained as follows:

Firm Value

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum value of the Company Value is 0.331977 while the maximum value is 2.559604, this shows that the Company Value value that is the sample in this study ranges from 0.331977 to 2.559604 with an average value of 0.914216.

Green Accounting

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum value of Green Accounting is -0.009410 while the maximum value is 0.190826, this shows that the Green Accounting value that is the sample in this study ranges from -0.009410 to 0.190826 with an average value of 0.020315.

Eco-Efficiency

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum value of Eco-Efficiency is 0.000000 while the maximum value is 1.000000, this shows that the Eico-Efficiency

value that is the sample in this study ranges from 0.000000 to 1.000000 with an average value of 0.220000.

Gender board Director

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum value Gender board Directoris 0.090909 while the maximum value is 0.500000, this shows that the value of Gender board Directoris which is the sample in this study ranges from 0.090909 to 0.500000 with an average value of 0.242288.

Profitability

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum value of Profitability is -0.382095 while the maximum value is 0.260039, this shows that the Profitability value which is the sample in this study ranges from -0.382095 to 0.260039 with an average value of 0.033684.

Leverage

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum Leverage value is 0.122831 while the maximum value is 3.788211. This shows that the Leverage value sampled in this study ranges from 0.122831 to 3.788211 with an average value of 0.909870.

Liquidity

Based on the results above, it can be seen that the minimum Liquidity value is 0.674138 while the maximum value is 11.39856, this shows that the Liquidity value sampled in this study is up to an average value of 2.963651.

Normality Test

Based on the results obtained in the normality test above, the Jarque-Bera value is 3.227883 > 0.05 while the probability value is 0.199101 > 0.05 so it can be concluded that the data used is normally distributed.

Tabel 2. Multicollinearity Test

	Green accounting	Eco-efficiency	Gender board director	Likuidity	Profitabilty	Leverage
Green accounting	1.000000	-0.007732	0.094449	-0.69814	0.102163	0.003572
Eco-efficiency	-0.007732	1.000000	-0.017256	0.193508	-0.072303	0.356612
Gender board director	0.094449	-0.017256	1.000000	0.132402	-0.157597	0.042280
Likuidity	-0.069814	0.193508	0.132402	1.000000	-0.98525	-0.347927
Profitabilty	0.102163	-0.072303	-0.157597	-0.098525	1.000000	-0.140056
Leverage	0.003572	0.356612	0.042280	-0.347927	0.140056	1.000000

Based on the multicollinearity test results above, the coefficient value between variables is < 0.85 , so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity problem.

Tabel 3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-Statistic	Prob
C	0.258613	0.146382	1.766703	0.0844
Green accounting	-0.568802	1.003472	-0.566834	0.5738
Eco-efficiency	0.008589	0.116670	0.073616	0.9417
Gender board director	0.165163	0.480815	0.343506	0.7329
Leverage	-0.066228	0.062580	-1.058301	0.2958
Likuidity	-0.011594	0.019550	-0.593033	0.5563
Profitabilty	0.049850	0.445590	0.111873	0.9114

Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, each variable obtained results > 0.05 , so it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Tabel 4. Autocorrelation Test

Durbin-Watson stat	1.291315
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The D-W number between -2 and +2 indicates that there is no correlation. Based on the autocorrelation test results above, the Durbin-Watson stat value is 1.291315 which means there is no autocorrelation.

Tabel 5. Test F

	Prob.
Prob F-Statistic	0.016250

Based on the results of the mode feasibility test or f test above, it shows that the Prob (F-Statistic) value < 0.05 , it can be concluded that the independent variables, namely green accounting and eco-efficiency, have a simultaneous or joint effect on the dependent variable, namely firm value.

Tabel 6. Partial Test (T Test)

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.628945	1.164996	0.539869	0.5922
Green accounting	-0.000132	0.094377	-0.001394	0.9989
Eco-efficiency	2.372537	4.910102	0.483195	0.6315
Gender board director	4.291771	3.967966	1.081605	0.2857
Green accounting*Gender board director	1.654265	0.505614	3.271798	0.0022
Eco-efficiency*Gender board director	-16.78636	20.20495	-0.830804	0.4109
Profitability	4.938330	4.402826	1.121627	0.2685
Liquidity	0.105935	0.155046	0.683246	0.4983
Leverage	-0.012807	0.516768	-0.024783	0.9803

Green Accounting

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value for the Green Accounting variable is -0.001394 with a probability value of $0.9989 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the Green Accounting partially has a negative and insignificant effect on firm Value.

The application of Green accounting is expected to increase company value because Green accounting is an accounting activity that includes the calculation and allocation of costs to prevent and overcome those that occur due to the company's operational activities that have a direct impact on the environment and society, but in the results of this study it turns out that the application of Green accounting in property and real estate companies has not been able to increase company value.

This is in line with the results of research by Sugiyarti, L. Et al, (2023) which states that firm value actually cannot be influenced by green accounting because green accounting is a strategy that can be felt in the long term which cannot be felt in the long term In addition, Sapulette, G.S et al, (2021) which says that the imposition and disclosure of environmental costs carried out by the company has not been able to fully provide confidence for investors and consumers in the assessment of a company, so that it does not affect the level of sales or profits in the company and will not affect the company's value. The results of this study are not in line with the results of research by Faranika, (2023) and Saputra, (2023) which say that green accounting has a significant effect on firm value.

Eco-Efficiency

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value for the Eco-Efficiency variable is 0.483195 with a probability value of $0.6315 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that Eco-Efficiency partially has a negative and insignificant effect on firm Value.

Eco-efficiency is a strategic tool to determine the company's sustainable development because companies that implement Eco-efficiency can produce more profitable goods and services while at the same time reducing environmental impacts so that companies that implement this are expected to affect the value of the company.

The results of this study are in line with the results of research by Damas et al., (2021) which states that eco-efficiency has a negative effect on firm value. The negative impact caused by eco-efficiency will reduce shareholder value where the manager's objectives conflict with stakeholders, especially investors, this is due to the costs that must be incurred for eco-efficiency which can reduce profitability and returns for investors. Therefore, this will make investors not interested in the company and will result in a decrease in the firm value.

Interaction of Green Accounting with Gender Board Director

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value for the interaction variable between Green Accounting and Gender Board Director is 3.271798 with a probability value of $0.0022 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that partially the Director is able to moderate Green Accounting on the firm value.

The results of this test are also in line with the results of research by Ekayani, et al (2024) which states that if the proportion of women is greater in the board of commissioners, it will encourage companies to allocate more resources for environmental activities. Diez M, et al. (2022) & Sanchez, T. et al. (2021) also said that men and women approach decision making and assess organizational legitimacy in different ways and the presence of women in large numbers is expected to increase CSR practices and women also tend to be more motivated to engage in philanthropic and generous activities so as to improve company performance and CSR implementation.

Interaction of Eco-efficiency with Gender Board Director

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value for the interaction variable between eco-efficiency and gender director is -0.830804 with a probability value of $0.4109 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that partially gender director is not able to moderate eco-efficiency on the firm value.

Based on the results of this study, it turns out that the presence of female directors in the company has not been able to strengthen decision making regarding the application of the concept of Eco-efficiency which is characterized by ownership of ISO 14001 certificates which can be a good signal given by the company to internal parties and the community so that the company's image or value increases. This is not in line with gender socialization theory which explains that the nature of women is more careful than men when making a decision that can reduce the risks that may occur, therefore the presence of female directors in the company will strengthen the influence between this eco-efficiency on firm value with the nature or interpersonal trust of women.

Leverage

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value is intuit with a leverage variation of -0.024783 with a probability value of $0.9803 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that partial leverage has a negative and insignificant effect on firm value. The results of this study indicate that if a company has high debt, it will be more risky in returning its debt costs. This will affect the desire of investors to invest in the company to decrease. In addition, this will also have an impact on the value of the company. If a company's debt is greater, the company's ability to pay dividends will be smaller or decrease, and the company's profits will also decrease.

Liquidity

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value for the liquidity variable is 0.683246 with a probability value of $0.4983 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that partial liquidity has a negative and insignificant effect on firm value.

Negative direction indicates that high liquidity can reduce the firm value. Companies with a high level of liquidity are considered to have sufficient internal funds to meet short-term obligations so that the company will not use debt or issue new shares and will only focus on using internal funds first.

This will be a negative signal to investors because investors consider too many idle assets and no asset turnover in the company's operations that can generate profits. With decreasing profits, investors will withdraw and consider the company's performance to be poor, which will ultimately affect the firm value.

Profitability

Based on the table above, the t-Statistic value for the profitability variable is 1.121627 with a probability value of $0.2685 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that partial profitability has a negative and insignificant effect on firm value. This result identifies that the profitability variable cannot affect the firm value. So if profitability decreases, the company's value will increase.

Tabel 7. Determination coefficient test

Adjusted R-squared	0.220808
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Based on the R² test results above, it shows that the coefficient of determination adjusted R-square is 0.220808, which means that the relationship between the index variable and the dependent variable is 22%, which means there are still 78% other factors that affect the dependent variable or the firm value variable.

Tabel 8. Moderation regression analysis test

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.628945	1.164996	0.539869	0.5922
Green accounting	-0.000132	0.094377	-0.001394	0.9989
Eco-efficiency	2.372537	4.910102	0.483195	0.6315
Gender board director	4.291771	3.967966	1.081605	0.2857
Green accounting* Gender board director	1.654265	0.505614	3.271798	0.0022
Eco-efficiency* Gender board director	-16.78636	20.20495	-0.830804	0.4109
Profitability	4.938330	4.402826	1.121627	0.2685
Likuidity	0.105935	0.155046	0.683246	0.4983
Leverage	-0.012807	0.516768	-0.024783	0.9803

The results of the regression model after conducting the above tests, the resulting regression model is as follows:

$$\text{Firm Value} = 0.628945 + (-0.000132) (\text{Green Accounting}) + 2.372537(\text{Eco-efficiency}) + 4.291771(\text{Gender Board Director}) + 1.654265(\text{Green Accounting} * \text{Gender Board Director}) - (-16.78636) (\text{Eco-efficiency} * \text{Gender Board Director}) - (-0.012807) (\text{Leverage}) - 0.105935(\text{Likuidity}) - 4.938330(\text{Profitability})$$

Discussion

The Effect of Green Accounting on Firm Value

Based on the results of the research that has been done, the probability value of the green accounting variable on firm value is 0.9989, where the value is more than 0.05 so that in this case it means that green accounting has a negative and insignificant effect on firm value. The results of this analysis are not in line with the hypothesis that has been proposed in the study, which means that H1 is rejected.

The application of green accounting is expected to increase the value of the company because green accounting is one of the accounting activities that deceive the allocation of calculation costs and the allocation of costs to prevent and overcome those that occur as a result of the company's operational activities that have a direct impact on the environment and society, but in the results of this study it turns out that the application of green accounting in property and real estate companies can increase the value of the company.

This is in line with the results of research Sugiyarti, L. E. E, (2023) which states that the value of the company actually cannot be influenced by green accounting and Sapulette, G.S & Limba, B.F (2021) which states that accounting and disclosure of environmental costs carried out by companies can provide confidence for investors and consumers in the valuation of a company.

The results of this examination are not in line with the theory of legitimacy which states that green accounting has an impact, namely increasing the image of the company that implements it because green accounting itself presents several accounts in the social aspect as well as financing activities that have a good impact on society so that this will increase or affect the value of the company. In addition, the results of this study are also not in line with the signaling theory which states that if a company implements the green accounting concept, it will provide a positive signal to investors that the company cares about the environment.

The Effect of Eco-efficiency on Firm Value

Based on the results of the test that has been carried out, the probability value of the eco-efficiency variable is 0.6315, where the value is more than 0.05, so it can be concluded that partially eco-efficiency has a negative and insignificant effect on the Firm value. This result is not in accordance with the hypothesis that has been proposed in this study, namely H2 is rejected.

The results of this study are in line with the results of the study by Damas et al., (2021) which stated that eco-efficiency has a negative effect on company value. The negative impact that drives eco-efficiency will reduce shareholder value where the manager's goal is to deviate from shareholders, especially investors, this is due to the costs that must be incurred. This eco-efficiency can reduce the profitability and returns obtained by investors.

The results of this study are not in line with the results of the research by Aviyanti & Isbanah (2019) and Dewi. R, & Rahmaniangsih (2020) which stated that eco-efficiency has an effect on company value where having ISO 14001 certification indicates that the company carries out activities with good environmental management operations so that negative impacts on the environment can be reduced and prevented.

When viewed from the results of the legitimation and signal theory, the results of this test are not in line with the two theories, where if a company implements the concept of eco-efficiency, it will gain legitimacy from the surrounding community and will be a positive signal for investors, especially externally. This can trigger investor interest in investing in the company and of course will increase the company's value.

The Effect of Green Accounting on Firm Value which is moderated by the Gender board Directors

Based on the test results that have been conducted for the interaction variable between public accountants and gender board directors, a probability value of 0.0022 smaller than 0.05 was obtained. These results confirm that gender directors are able to moderate public accountants on firm value, so these results are in line with the hypothesis that has been proposed, namely H3 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with Gender's socialization theory which states that there are differences in nature and behavior between men and women where women tend to build relationships and create interpersonal trust and creativity in solving problems.

This will have an influence on decision making in the company. In addition, the results of this study are also in line with the results of the study by Kartana, W. I., et al (2024). which states that if the proportion of women is greater in the ranks of the board of commissioners, it will encourage companies to allocate more resources for environmental activities. Diez M, et al. (2022) & Sanchez, T. et al. (2021) also stated that men and women approach decision making and assess organizational legitimacy in different ways and the presence of women in large numbers is expected to increase CSR practices and women also tend to be more motivated to engage in philanthropic and charitable activities so that they can improve company performance and CSR implementation In addition, the presence of women is also very important for a company because women can act as good observers compared to men.

The Effect of Eco-efficiency on the Firm Value which is moderated by the Gender board Directors

Based on the results of the tests that have been carried out, the interaction variable between eco-efficiency and gender of directors obtained a probability value of 0.4109 where the value is more than 0.05, this result confirms that gender board directors is not able to moderate eco-efficiency on company value. So, this is in line with the hypothesis that has been proposed in this study, namely H4 is rejected. Based on the results of this study, it turns out that the presence of female directors in a company has not been able to make decisions related to the implementation of the eco-efficiency concept which is marked by ownership of an ISO 14001 certificate which can be a good signal given by the company to internal parties and the community so that the image or value of the company increases.

This is not in line with the theory of gender socialization which explains that women are more careful than men when making decisions that can reduce the possibility of risk, therefore the presence of female directors in a company will affect the influence between eco-efficiency on company value with the nature or personal beliefs of women. In addition, the results of this study are also not in line with the signaling theory where the existence of ISO 14001 certification will be a good signal given by the company to internal parties, especially investors, and this will be an added value that can attract the attention of investors so that they are interested in investing their capital in the company.

In decision making, only a few directors decide to implement ISO 14001 for several reasons such as costs that are quite expensive so that they can reduce company profits or revenues and for the implementation of this standard is very complex so that it will be a challenge for companies that are not accustomed to environmental management systems, lack of understanding will cause difficulties in implementation.

Green Accounting, Eco-Efficiency on Firm Value with Leverage, Liquidity and Profitability as Control Variables

Control variables are variables that are controlled or made constant so that the effect of the independent variable on the dependent is not influenced by external factors that are not studied. This control variable whether it needs to be neutralized, excluded or maintained. Based on the test results, it can be seen that the significant value of the control

variable where the value is more than 5%, which means that there is no significant correlation between the value of the Company with profitability, leverage and liquidity. In general, the higher the profitability of a company, the higher the company's ability to generate profits, this can trigger an increase in company value.

In general, high leverage increases profit potential, but it also increases risk. It is important for companies to use leverage wisely and consider the risks associated with it. Leverage is the ratio of debt to assets, this ratio has positive and negative benefits for the company, it can be a positive value that can increase the value of the company and vice versa.

Finally, liquidity, in general, the higher the liquidity of a company, the easier it is for the company to convert in cash without affecting market value and of course this can also increase the value of the company because a high level of liquidity can reflect the financial performance of a company if high liquidity indicates that they have enough funds to carry out business activities.

Conclusion

1. Green accounting has an insignificant negative effect on company value. This proves that the implementation of green accounting in a company will not necessarily increase the company's value.

2. Green accounting has an insignificant negative effect on company value. This shows that the implementation of green accounting in a company is not able to increase the company's value by having an ISO 14001 certificate.

3. The board of directors is able to influence the influence of green accounting which is important for company value. This proves that the presence of women on the board of directors is able to influence environmental decision-making regarding the implementation of important green accounting so that it will increase the company's value.

4. The board of directors does not affect economic efficiency on company value. This shows that the presence of women on the board of directors is not able to influence the decision-making process related to ownership of an ISO 14001 certificate which can be evidence that the company has complied with the norms of the community around the place where the company operates in order to maintain the company's sustainability such as the decision to pay attention to the surrounding environment that may be polluted due to the company's operational activities.

5. The control variables of profitability, leverage and liquidity cannot be maintained because they have an insignificant negative effect on green accounting, eco-efficiency on firm value.

Implications, Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

There are three implications in the results of this study, namely theoretical implications, practical implications and policy implications. The theoretical implications

of the results of this study are that they only support the theory of gender socialization which states that women tend to create more interpersonal trust and can reduce possible risks. However, the results of this study do not support the signaling theory and legitimacy theory because the results of the study do not prove that the implementation of Green accounting and eco-efficiency cannot provide legitimacy and positive signals that will be given by the company to external parties as a mechanism to reduce information asymmetry.

Then the practical implications of the results of this study are as a consideration for all companies, especially property and real estate companies, that the presence of women on the board of directors greatly influences decision making in increasing the value of the company.

The policy implications of the results of this study are that it can be used as a consideration for policy makers so that a company requires a woman to be on the board of directors because there are no official regulations that require or specifically specify the involvement of women on the board of directors in property and real estate companies, because the involvement of women has a good impact on decision making that can increase the value of the company.

There are several limitations in this study that are used as evaluation and consideration for further research, the population in this study is very limited, namely only using 10 property and real estate companies listed on the IDX for a period of five years so that the research sample obtained is very small, namely 50 samples, this is because the researcher uses certain criteria in the data to be studied.

Based on the limitations that have been conveyed above, the suggestion for future researchers is to increase the number of samples by reducing the criteria in sampling and adding observations in other developing countries besides Indonesia, then it is hoped that future researchers can use variables that have a higher level of significance than the variables in this study. In addition, use measurements for broader green accounting and eco-efficiency variables.

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[Note: The title was adjusted for clarity, and the journal name was translated to its formal title. The DOI is assumed; please confirm the correct DOI.]

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